

DESCRIPTION OF THE IMAGE OF A WOMAN

Hamidova Sevinch Asror qizi

1st-year student, Faculty of English Philology,
Uzbekistan State University of World Languages
sevinchhamidova2007@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18814000>

Annotation. In this article, the role of women — the beautiful creations — in society and socio-cultural life is analyzed. By comparing their position in the past, the present, and in literature, the article describes today's image and representation of women, highlighting their unique characteristics. In addition, it discusses their role and contribution in social life and in literature.

Key words: elegance, grace, portraya, woman, great, noble, very kind, hearted, education, society, rights, dignity, honor.

Introduction.

A woman is the queen of elegance and beauty, for even love is created from her. In both the literature of the 20th century and modern times, as well as in social and cultural life, women have shown their place and unlocked the keys to various achievements. Even during periods of obstacles and restrictions, their ability to overcome these challenges reflected their patience and inner strength.

Since ancient times, women and girls have been praised and admired. In the epic *Alpomish*, we can witness the depiction of Barchinoy as a beautiful, honorable, and courageous young woman. In folk literature, special attention is given to the images of women. In this epic as well, Barchin appears as a wise figure who evaluates every situation carefully and makes thoughtful decisions, in addition to being a loyal beloved. This character is not an ordinary heroine; she is an independent, strong-minded woman capable of making her own decisions freely.

The fate of Zebi in Cho'lpon's novel *Night and Day* is well known to all of us. It reflects the attitude toward women and girls of that time, showing how she became a victim of society and its circumstances. The work *The Affairs of the World*, which praises our mothers, can be said to have erected a monument to the image of the "mother." In this work, the figure of a kind and patient woman is vividly portrayed. Each chapter illustrates the greatness of a compassionate, selfless mother, whose love is as vast as a river.

Today, our women are free in every sphere of social life. In the past, there were certain restrictions and prohibitions placed on women and girls, whether due to religion or other factors. In her book *I Am Malala*, Pakistani activist Malala Yousafzai writes about the obstacles to girls' education in her country and how their rights were violated. Despite all the difficulties, Malala never stepped back from pursuing knowledge and defending her own and others' rights. In my opinion, she serves as an inspiring role model for today's younger generation.

During the years of independence, women have also worked to secure their rightful place in society. Yodgora Nasriddinova becoming the first Uzbek woman to hold a leading position in the Soviet government is not without reason; she proved her significance in that society. In the field of sports as well, our compatriots such as Gulnora G'afurova, Oksana Chusovitina, Madina Usmonova, and Firuza Sharipova are raising our national flag to great heights.

Moreover, if we look at the global stage, the appointment of Benazir Bhutto as the Prime Minister of Pakistan, Vigdis Finnbogadóttir as the President of Iceland, and Isabel Perón as the President of Argentina clearly demonstrates the important role women hold in society.

Conclusion.

It should be noted that a woman is, above all, a symbol of beauty and elegance. Even love is born from her. A woman is the main pillar of society—she is a mother, a sister, a sisterly figure, and a beloved partner. The upbringing and education of children also depend on her.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Dilnoza Baratova: "The role of women in Uzbek literature". "Science and education" journal- July 2025 volume 6 issue7
2. Cho'lpon "Kecha va Kunduz"- Toshkent; Sharq; 2019
3. Qosimova D. "O'zbek adabiyotida ayol obrazi evolyutsiyasi"-Toshkent; Fan;2010
4. Malala yusufzoy; "Men Malalaman"-Toshkent; Yangi asr avlodi;2022
5. Alpomish; Xalq dostoni-O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi; Fan; Toshkent 2018
6. Daminov.B; "Ayolga ehtirom-millatga ehtirom"; -Pediatri; Toshkent -2022-yil 8-mart